

A Review on Recent Development of Neutro-Topology

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Abstract: Smarandache proposed NeutroAlgebra and AntiAlgebra. NeutroAlgebras and AntiAlgebras are a new research topic based on real-world scenarios. He investigated the concepts of neutro- and anti-structure. He demonstrated using NeutroAlgebra concepts that just because a statement is completely true in a classical Algebra does not imply that it is also completely true in a NeutroAlgebra or AntiAlgebra. It is determined by the operations and axioms on which it is based (whether they are completely true, partially true, totally false, or partially or completely indeterminate). This study examines the concepts of Generalised regular Neutro-Topological space and its properties.

Keywords: Neutro-Topology; NeutroClosed sets; NeutroOpen sets; GR-NeutroInterior.

1. Introduction

Topology is a significant subject of Mathematics, hence it is surprising that topology's appreciation was delayed in the history of Mathematics. Topology is the study of space characteristics that are unaffected by continuous deformation.

A key idea in mathematics, set theory, dates back to the work of Russian mathematician George Cantor (1877). We were able to investigate a variety of mathematical ideas thanks to set theory. However, there are a lot of unknowns in our life. The traditional logic of mathematics is frequently insufficient to resolve these difficulties. Then the idea of fuzzy sets was introduced by Zadeh [1]. It is a development of the traditional idea of a set. In his paper, he presented a hypothesis according to which fuzzy sets are sets with imprecise boundaries. In both directions, gradual changes from membership to non membership can be expressed using fuzzy sets. It offers meaningful representations of vague notions in everyday language in addition to a powerful and meaningful way to quantify uncertainties. a value in the discourse universe that indicates the fuzzy set's degree of membership. Real values in the closed range of 0 to 1 are used to represent these membership classifications. Chang [2] discovered and popularized the theory of fuzzy topological spaces. The concepts for creating fuzzy topological spaces were provided by Lowen [3]. He provided the idea of fuzzy compression and two new functions, which allowed for the evident observation of further relationships between fuzzy topological spaces and topological spaces. A unique fuzzy topological space called the product spaces was discussed by Cheng-Ming [4]. He established a type of fuzzy points neighbourhood formation, such as the Q-neighbourhood, which is a crucial idea in fuzzy topological spaces. He also demonstrated how each fuzzy topological space is isomorphic topologically by a specific space of topology.

Atanassov [5] introduced the concept of intuitionistic fuzzy sets as an extension of sets with better applicability. Coker [6] developed the idea of intuitionistic smooth fuzzy topological spaces using the concept of intuitionistic fuzzy sets. The definitions of the intuitionistic smooth fuzzy topological spaces were first presented by Samanta and Mondal [7].

Smarandache [8] introduced the concept of a neutrosophic set for the first time. These concepts have three different degrees: T for membership, I for uncertainty, and F for non-membership. In other words, a situation is treated in neutrosophy in accordance with its trueness, falsity, and uncertainty. As a result, neutrosophic sets and logic enable us to make sense of a variety of uncertainties in our daily lives. On this topic, numerous studies have been conducted. Sahin et al. recently discovered some operations for neutrosophic sets with interval values; Neutrosophic multigroups and applications were researched by Ulucay et al [9]; Q-neutrosophic soft expert set and its application were introduced by Hassan et al [10]. The acquisition of neutrosophic soft expert sets was introduced by Sahin et al [11]; Interval-valued refined neutrosophic sets and their applications were researched by Ulucay et al [12]. Neutrosophic set importance on deep transfer learning techniques was obtained by Khalifa et al. [13]; Generalised Hamming similarity measure based on neutrosophic quadruple numbers and its applications were researched by Kargin et al. [14]; In order to assess the quality of online education, Sahin et al. [15] obtain Hausdorff Measures on generalised set valued neutrosophic quadruple numbers and decision-making applications. The foundation for a wide family of novel mathematical ideas, including both their crisp and fuzzy counterparts, was laid by neutrosophy. The concepts of neutrosophic crisp set and neutrosophic crisp topological space were first developed by Salama et al. and Alblowi [16]. Neutron structures and antistructures are defined by Smarandache [17]. An algebraic structure can be divided into three regions, similar to neutrosophic logic: A, the set of elements that satisfy the conditions of the algebraic structure, the truth region; Neutro A, the set of elements that do not meet the conditions of the algebraic structure, the uncertainty region; and anti-A, the set of elements that do not satisfy the conditions of the algebraic structure, the inaccuracy region. By eliminating neutrosophic sets and neutrosophic numbers, the structure of neutrosophic logic has been translated to the structure of classical algebras. The academic world has seen a rise in interest in neutrosophic set theory research in recent years. As a result, it is possible to generate neutro-algebraic structures, which are more broadly structured than classical algebras. Additionally, the region of elements that do not conform to any of the classical algebras is also considered to have anti-algebraic structures. Recent research includes studies on neutro-algebra by Smarandache et al. [18], the neutrosophic triplet of BI-algebras by Razaeei et al. [19], neutro-bck-algebra by Smarandache et al. [20], and neutro-hypergroups by Ibrahim et al. [21].

In this paper, we introduce new Generalization of Regular Neutro-open (briefly, GRN-open) sets and Generalised regular Anti-open set. This new class shows stronger properties in general topological spaces that mean GRN-open sets exists in between the class of regular open sets and the class of open sets. Also, we investigate GRN-neighbourhood, GRN-interior and GRN-closure properties.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. The NeuroSophication of the Law [22]

1. Let X be a non-empty set and $*$ be a binary operation. For some elements $(a, b) \in (X, X)$, $(a*b) \in X$ (degree of well defined (T)) and for other elements $(x, y), (p, q) \in (X, X)$; $[x*y$ is indeterminate (degree of indeterminacy (I)), or $p*q \notin X$ (degree of outer-defined (F))], where (T, I, F) is different from $(1,0,0)$ that represents the Classical Law, and from $(0,0,1)$ that represents the Anti Law.
2. In Neutro Algebra, the classical well-defined for binary operation $*$ is divided into three regions: degree of well-defined (T), degree of indeterminacy (I) and degree of outer-defined (F) similar to neutrosophic set and neutrosophic logic.

Definition 2.2. [23]

Let X be the non-empty set and τ be a collection of subsets of X . Then τ is said to be a Neutro Topology on X and the pair (X, τ) is said to be a Neutro Topological space, if at least one of the following conditions hold good:

1. $[(\emptyset_N \in \tau, X_N \notin \tau) \text{ or } (X_N \in \tau, \emptyset_N \notin \tau)]$ or $[\emptyset_N, X_N \in \sim \tau]$
2. For some n elements $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n \in \tau, \bigcap_{i=1}^n a_i \in \tau$ [degree of truth T] and for other n elements $b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n \in \tau, p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n \in \tau$; $[(\bigcap_{i=1}^n b_i \notin \tau)$ [degree of falsehood F] or $(\bigcap_{i=1}^n p_i$ is indeterminate (degree of indeterminacy I)], where n is finite; [where (T, I, F) is different from $(1,0,0)$ that represents the Classical Axiom, and from $(0,0,1)$ that represents the Anti Axiom].
3. For some n elements $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n \in \tau, \bigcup_{i=1}^n a_i \in \tau$ [degree of truth T] and for other n elements $b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n \in \tau, p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n \in \tau$; $[(\bigcup_{i=1}^n b_i \notin \tau)$ [degree of falsehood F] or $(\bigcup_{i=1}^n p_i$ is indeterminate (degree of indeterminacy I)], where n is finite; [where (T, I, F) is different from $(1,0,0)$ that represents the Classical Axiom, and from $(0,0,1)$ that represents the Anti Axiom].

Definition 2.3. [23]

Let X be the non-empty set and τ be a collection of subsets of X . Then τ is said to be an Anti Topology on X and the pair (X, τ) is said to be an Anti Topological space, if at least one of the following conditions hold good:

1. $\emptyset_N, X_N \notin \tau$
2. For n elements $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n \in \tau, \bigcap_{i=1}^n a_i \notin \tau$ [degree of falsehood F] where n is finite.
3. For some n elements $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n \in \tau, \bigcup_{i=1}^n a_i \notin \tau$ [degree of falsehood F] where n is finite.

Remark 2.1. [23]

The symbol " $\in \sim$ " will be used for situations where it is an unclear appurtenance (not sure if an element belongs or not to a set). For example, if it is not certain whether " a " is a member of the set P , then it is denoted by $a \in \sim P$.

Main Works

3. GR-NeutroOpen sets and their properties

We introduce GR-NeutroOpen sets and investigate some of relationships between existed classes.

Definition 3.1. A NeutroSubset M of space P is called Generalized Regular Neutrosophic Open (briefly, GR-NeutroOpen) set if $M = \text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(M))$. We denote the class of sets as GRNO(P).

Firstly we have to prove the existence of new class GR-NeutroOpen sets in topological spaces.

Theorem 3.1. Every regular NeutroOpen set is GR-NeutroOpen set.

Proof. Let M be a regular NeutroOpen set in P . To prove that M is GR- NeutroOpen in P .

We know that

$$M \subseteq g\text{-NeuCl}(M) \subseteq \text{NeuCl}(M) \text{ that is } \text{NeuInt}(M) \subseteq \text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(M)) \subseteq \text{NeuInt}(\text{cl}(M)).$$

As M is regular NeutroOpen, $M = \text{NeuInt}(\text{cl}(M))$ and $\text{NeuInt}(M) = M$.

Hence $M \subseteq \text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(M)) \subseteq \text{NeuInt}(\text{NeuCl}(M)) = M$,

Thus $\text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(M)) = M$. Therefore M is GR- NeutroOpen in P .

The converse of above theorem need not be true.

Example 3.1. Let $P = \{1,2,3,4\}$ with the topology on it $\tau = \{P, \emptyset, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{1,2\}, \{2,3\}, \{1,2,3\}\}$, then sets $\{2\}$, $\{1,2\}$ are NeutroOpen sets but not regular NeutroOpen sets in P .

Theorem 3.2. Every GR-NeutroOpen set is NeutroOpen set.

Proof. Let M be a GR- NeutroOpen set in P . That is $M = \text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(M))$. As interior of any subset of P is an NeutroOpen set, therefore M is a NeutroOpen in P .

The converse of above theorem need not be true.

Example 3.2. Let $P = \{1,2,3,4\}$ with the topology on it

$$\tau = \{P, \emptyset, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{1,2\}, \{2,3\}, \{1,2,3\}\}.$$

Then the set $\{1,2,3\}$ is NeutroOpen set but not GR- NeutroOpen in P .

Remark 3.1. From Theorem 3.2, we know that every GR- NeutroOpen set is a NeutroOpen set but not conversely. We know that every NeutroOpen set is semi- NeutroOpen but not conversely. Hence every GR- NeutroOpen set is a semi- NeutroOpen set but not conversely.

Remark 3.2. From Theorem 3.2, we know that every NeutroOpen set is a NeutroOpen set but not conversely. We know that every NeutroOpen set is g - NeutroOpen but not conversely. Hence every GR- NeutroOpen set is a g - NeutroOpen set but not conversely.

Theorem 3.3. Intersection of two GR-NeutroOpen sets is a GR- NeutroOpen set in topological spaces.

Proof. Let M and N be two GR- NeutroOpen sets in space P . To prove that $M \cap N$ is GR-NeutroOpen set in space P , that is to prove that $M \cap N = \text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(M \cap N))$. As M and N are GR-

NeuroOpen sets in $P, M = \text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(M)), N = \text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(N))$. We know that $M \cap N \subseteq M$, $g\text{-NeuCl}(M \cap N) \subseteq g\text{-NeuCl}(M)$ also $M \cap N \subseteq N$, $g\text{-NeuCl}(M \cap N) \subseteq g\text{-NeuCl}(N)$. Which implies $\text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(M \cap N)) \subseteq \text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(M))$ and $\text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(M \cap N)) \subseteq \text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(N))$. This implies $\text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(M \cap N)) \cap \text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(M \cap N)) \subseteq \text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(M)) \cap \text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(N))$ That is $\text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(M \cap N)) \subseteq \text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(M)) \cap \text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(N)) = M \cap N \dots$ (i) $M \cap N = \text{NeuInt}(M) \cap \text{NeuInt}(N) = \text{NeuInt}(M \cap N)$ [$M = \text{NeuInt}(M)$ and $N = \text{NeuInt}(N)$] because of if M and N are NeuroOpen sets, then every NeuroOpen is NeuroOpen in P] $\text{NeuInt}(M \cap N) \subseteq \text{NeuInt}(g\text{-cl}(A \cap B))$. $M \cap N \subseteq \text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(M \cap N)) \dots$ (ii) From (i) and (ii), $M \cap N = \text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(M \cap N))$. Hence $M \cap N$ is GR- NeuroOpen set in P .

Remark 3.3. The union of two GR- NeuroOpen sets is generally not a GR- NeuroOpen set in topological spaces.

Example 3.3. Let $P = \{1,2,3,4\}$ with topology on it

$\tau = \{P, \emptyset, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{1,2\}, \{2,3\}, \{1,2,3\}\}$. If $M = \{1,2\}$ and

$N = \{2,3\}$ are GR-open sets in P but $M \cap N = \{2\}$ is not GR- NeuroOpen set in P .

Theorem 3.4. If M is a GR- NeuroOpen then $\text{NeuInt}(M) = M$.

Proof. Let M is GR-NeuroOpen. To prove $\text{NeuInt}(M) = M$. We know that every GR- NeuroOpen set is NeuroOpen, that is M is NeuroOpen set then $\text{NeuInt}(M) = M$. The converse of above theorem need not be true.

Example 3.4. Let $P = \{1,2,3,4\}$ with topology on it $\tau = \{P, \emptyset, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{1,2\}, \{1,2,3\}\}$, then $\text{GRNO}(P) = \{P, \emptyset, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{1,2\}\}$. Then the Neuro-set $M = \{1,2,3\}$, Note that $\text{NeuInt}(M) = \{1,2,3\}$ is not a GR- NeuroOpen set, but it is NeuroOpen set of P .

Theorem 3.5. If M is g -closed and NeuroOpen in P , then M is GR- NeuroOpen in P .

Proof. Let M is g -closed and NeuroOpen in P . To prove that M is GR- NeuroOpen i.e. to prove $M = \text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(M))$. Now $g\text{-NeuCl}(M) = M$, because M is g - NeuroOpen set. As $\text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(M)) = \text{NeuInt}(M)$ this implies $\text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(M)) = M$, because M is NeuroOpen set. Then M is GR- NeuroOpen in P .

Remark 3.4. Complement of a GR-NeuroOpen set need not be GR- NeuroOpen set.

Example 3.5. Let $P = \{1,2,3,4\}$ with topology on it $\tau = \{P, \emptyset, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{1,2\}, \{2,3\}, \{1,2,3\}\}$. Note that $\{1,2\}$ is a

GR- NeuroOpen set. But $P - \{1,2\} = \{3\}$ is not a GR- NeuroOpen set in P .

4. GR-NeuroClosed sets and their properties

We introduce GR-NeuroClosed sets and investigate some of their properties.

Definition 4.1. A subset M of space P is called Generalized Regular Neutrosophic Closed (briefly, GR-NeutroClosed) set if $P - M$ is GR- NeutroClosed in P . Then its family is denoted as GRNC(P).

This new class of sets properly lies between the class of regular NeutroClosed sets and the class of NeutroClosed sets

Theorem 4.1. A subset M of P is GR- NeutroClosed if and only if $M = \text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(M))$.

Proof. (i) Suppose M is GR- NeutroClosed. To prove $M = \text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(M))$. As M is GR-NeutroClosed, $P - M$ is GR-NeutroOpen in P , which implies $P - M = \text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(P - M))$. $P - M = \text{NeuInt}(P - g\text{-NeuInt}(M))$. [because $g\text{-NeuCl}(P - M) = P - g\text{-NeuCl}(M)$] = $P - \text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(M))$. So $(P - M)^c = [P - \text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(M))]^c$. That is $M = \text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(M))$. (ii) Suppose $M = \text{NeuCl}(g\text{-Int}(M))$. To prove M is GR- NeutroClosed, [That is to prove $P - M$ is GR-NeutroOpen set]. That is $P - M = \text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(M))$. Now given $M = \text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(M))$. $P - M = P - \text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(M))$. $P - M = \text{NeuInt}(g\text{-NeuCl}(P - M))$. implies that $P - M$ is GR-NeutroOpen set that is M is GR- NeutroClosed in P .

Theorem 4.2. Every regular NeutroClosed set is GR- NeutroClosed set.

Proof. Let M be a regular NeutroClosed set in space P . Then M^c is a regular NeutroOpen set. By Theorem 3.1, M^c is GR- NeutroOpen set. Therefore M is a GR- NeutroClosed set in P .

The converse of above theorem need not be true.

Example 4.1. From Example 3.1, the set $\{3,4\}$ and $\{1,3,4\}$ are GR- NeutroClosed sets but not regular NeutroClosed in P .

Theorem 4.3. Every GR- NeutroClosed set is NeutroClosed set.

Proof. Let M be a GR- NeutroClosed set in P . Then M^c is a GR- NeutroOpen in P . By Theorem 3.2, M^c is an NeutroOpen set in P . Therefore M is a NeutroClosed set in P .

The converse of above theorem need not be true.

Example 4.2. From Example 3.1, the set $\{4\}$ is NeutroClosed set but not GR- NeutroClosed set in P .

Remark 4.1. From Theorem 4.3, we have, every GR- NeutroClosed set is a NeutroClosed set but not conversely. Also, every NeutroClosed set is semi- NeutroClosed set but not conversely. Hence every GR- NeutroClosed set is a semi- NeutroClosed set but not conversely.

Remark 4.2. From Theorem 4.3, we have, every GR- NeutroClosed set is a NeutroClosed set but not conversely. Every NeutroClosed set is NeutroClosed but not conversely. Hence every GR-NeutroClosed set is NeutroClosed set but not conversely.

Remark 4.3. From Theorem 4.3, we know that every GR- NeutroClosed set is a NeutroClosed set but not conversely. It is clear that every NeutroClosed set is g - NeutroClosed but not conversely. Hence every GR- NeutroClosed set is a g - NeutroClosed set but not conversely.

Remark 4.4. The following example shows that GR- NeutroClosed sets are independent of ir-NeutroClosed sets, s -NeutroClosed sets and regular semi- NeutroOpen (=regular semi-NeutroClosed) sets.

Example 4.3. Let $P = \{1,2,3,4,5\}$ with topology on it

$\tau = \{P, \emptyset, \{1\}, \{1,4\}, \{2,3\}, \{1,2,3\}, \{1,2,3,4\}\}$. Then

NeuroClosed sets in P are $P, \emptyset, \{5\}, \{4,5\}, \{1,4,5\}, \{2,3,5\}, \{2,3,4,5\}$.

GR- NeuroClosed sets in P are $P, \emptyset, \{4,5\}, \{1,4,5\}, \{2,3,5\}, \{2,3,4,5\}$.

π - NeuroClosed sets in P are $P, \emptyset, \{5\}, \{1,4,5\}, \{2,3,5\}$.

s - NeuroClosed sets in P are $P, \emptyset, \{5\}, \{1,4,5\}, \{2,3,5\}$.

regular semi-NeuroOpen sets in P are $P, \emptyset, \{1,4\}, \{2,3\}, \{1,4,5\}, \{2,3,5\}$.

Theorem 4.4. Union of two GR- NeuroClosed sets is a GR- NeuroClosed set in topological spaces.

Proof. Let M and N be two GR- NeuroClosed sets in P . To prove that $M \cup N = \text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(M \cup N))$. As M and N are GR- NeuroClosed sets in P , $M = \text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(M))$, $N = \text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(N))$. We know that $M \subseteq M \cup N$, $g\text{-NeuInt}(M) \subseteq g\text{-NeuInt}(M \cup N)$ also $N \subseteq M \cup N$, $g\text{-NeuInt}(N) \subseteq g\text{-NeuInt}(M \cup N)$. Which implies $\text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(M)) \subseteq \text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(M \cup N))$ and $\text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(N)) \subseteq \text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(M \cup N))$. This implies $\text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(M)) \cup \text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(N)) \subseteq \text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(M \cup N)) \cup \text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(M \cup N))$. That is

$$\text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(M)) \cup \text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(N)) \subseteq \text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(M \cup N)) \dots (i)$$

$M \cup N = \text{NeuCl}(M) \cup \text{NeuCl}(N) = \text{NeuCl}(M \cup N)$ [$M = \text{NeuCl}(M)$ and $N = \text{NeuCl}(N)$ and M, N are NeuroClosed sets, because every GR- NeuroClosed is NeuroClosed set] $\text{NeuCl}(M \cup N) \supseteq \text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(M \cup N))$ i.e. $M \cup N \supseteq \text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(M \cup N)) \dots (ii)$

From (i) and (ii), $M \cup N = \text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(M \cup N))$. Hence $M \cup N$ is GR- NeuroClosed set in P . Hence $A \cup B$ is GR- NeuroClosed in X .

Remark 4.5 The intersection of two GR- NeuroClosed sets in topological spaces is generally not a GR- NeuroClosed set.

Example 4.4. From Example 3.1, then sets $M = \{1,4\}$ and $N = \{3,4\}$ are GR- NeuroClosed sets in P but $M \cap N = \{4\}$ is not GR- NeuroClosed set in P .

Theorem 4.5. If M is a GR- NeuroClosed if and only if $\text{NeuCl}(M) = M$.

Proof. If M is GR- NeuroClosed. To prove $\text{NeuCl}(M) = M$. We know that every GR- NeuroClosed set is NeuroClosed set i.e. M is NeuroClosed then $\text{NeuCl}(M) = M$.

The converse of above theorem need not be true.

Example 4.5. Let $P = \{1,2,3,4\}$ with topology on it $\tau = \{P, \emptyset, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{1,2\}, \{1,2,3\}\}$. Then $\text{GRNC}(P) = \{P, \emptyset, \{3,4\}, \{1,3,4\}, \{2,3,4\}\}$. Then the set $M = \{4\}$. Note that $\text{NeuCl}(M) = \{4\}$ is not a GR- NeuroClosed set, but it is a NeuroClosed set of P .

Theorem 4.6. If M is g -NeuroOpen and NeuroClosed in P , then M is GR- NeuroClosed set in P .

Proof. Let M is g -NeuroOpen and NeuroClosed set in P . To prove that

M is GR- NeuroClosed set i.e. to prove $M = \text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(M))$. Now $g\text{-NeuInt}(M) = M$, because M is g -NeuroOpen set. As $\text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(M)) = \text{NeuCl}(M)$ this implies $\text{NeuCl}(g\text{-NeuInt}(M)) = M$, because M is NeuroClosed set. Then M is GR- NeuroClosed set in P .

5. GR-NeuroNeighbourhoods and GR-NeuroInterior

Definition 5.1. (i) Let P be a topological space and $x \in P$, A subset N of P is said to be a GR-NeuroNeighbourhood (briefly, GR-NeuNhd) of x if and only if there exists a GR-NeuroOpen set G such that $x \in G \subseteq N$.

(ii) The collection of all GR-NeuroNeighbourhood of $x \in P$ is GR-NeuroNeighbourhood system at x and is denoted by $GR-N(x)$.

Definition 5.2. Let M be a subset of P . A point $x \in M$ is said to be GR-NeuroInterior point of M if and only if P is a GR-NeuroNeighborhood of x . The set of all GR-NeuroInterior points of M is called the GR-NeuroInterior of M and is denoted as $GR-int(M)$.

Theorem 5.1. If M is a subset of P , then $GR-NeuroInt(M) = \cup\{G : G \text{ is GR-NeuroOpen set, } G \subseteq M\}$.

Proof. Let M be a subset of P . $x \in GR-NeuInt(A)$ implies that x is a GR-NeuroInterior point of P i.e. M is a GR-NeuNhd of point x . Then there exists a GR-NeuroOpen set G such that $x \in G \subseteq A$

implies that $x \in \cup\{G : G \text{ is GR-NeuroOpen set, } G \subseteq M\}$. Hence

$$GR-NeuInt(M) = \cup\{G : G \text{ is GR-NeuroOpen set, } G \subseteq M\}.$$

Theorem 5.2. Let P be a topological space and $M \subseteq P$, then show that M is GR-NeuroOpen set if and only if $GR-NeuInt(M) = M$.

Proof. Let M be a GR-NeuroOpen set in P . Then clearly the largest GR-NeuroOpen set contained in M , is itself M . Hence $GR-NeuInt(M) = M$.

Conversely, suppose that $M \subseteq P$ and $GR-NeuInt(M) = M$. Since $GR-NeuInt(M)$ is a GR-NeuroOpen set in P , it follows that M is a GR-NeuroOpen set in P .

Theorem 5.3. Let M and N are subset of P . Then

1. $GR-NeuInt(P) = P$ and $GR-NeuInt(\emptyset) = \emptyset$.
2. $GR-NeuInt(M) \subseteq M$.
3. If N is any GR-NeuroOpen set contained in M , then $N \subseteq GR-NeuInt(M)$.
4. If $M \subseteq N$, then $GR-NeuInt(M) \subseteq GR-NeuInt(N)$.
5. $GR-NeuInt(GR-NeuInt(M)) = GR-NeuInt(M)$.

Proof. (1) Since P and \emptyset are GR-NeuroOpen sets, by Theorem 5.3, $GR-NeuInt(P) = \cup\{G : G \text{ is GR-NeuroOpen set, } G \subseteq P\} = P \cup \{\text{all GR-NeuroOpen sets}\} = P$. That is $GR-NeuInt(P) = P$. Since \emptyset is the only GR-NeuroOpen set contained in \emptyset , $GR-NeuInt(\emptyset) = \emptyset$.

(2) Let $x \in GR-NeuInt(A)$ implies that x is a GR-NeuroInterior point of M . That is M is a GR-NeuNhd of x i.e. $x \in M$. Thus $x \in GR-int(A)$ implies $x \in A$. Hence $GR-NeuInt(M) \subseteq M$.

(3) Let N be any GR- NeutroOpen set such that $N \subseteq M$. Let $x \in N$. Since N is a GR-NeutroOpen set contained in M , x is a GR-NeuInterior point of M . That is $x \in \text{GR-NeuInt}(M)$. Hence $N \subseteq \text{GR-NeuInt}(M)$.

(4) Let M and N be subsets of P such that $M \subseteq N$. Let $x \in \text{GR-NeuInt}(M)$. Since $\text{GR-NeuInt}(M) \subseteq M$ and $M \subseteq N$, we have $\text{GR-NeuInt}(M) \subseteq N$. Now $\text{GR-NeuInt}(M)$ is a GR- NeutroOpen set and $\text{GR-NeuInt}(N)$ is the largest GR- NeutroOpen set contained in N , we have to find $\text{GR-NeuInt}(M) \subseteq \text{GR-NeuInt}(N)$.

(5) Since $\text{GR-NeuInt}(M)$ is a GR-NeutroOpen set in P , it follows that $\text{GR-NeuInt}(\text{GR-NeuInt}(M)) = \text{GR-NeuInt}(M)$.

Theorem 5.4. If M and N are subsets of P , then $\text{GR-NeuInt}(M) \cup \text{GR-NeuInt}(N) \subseteq \text{GR-NeuInt}(M \cup N)$.

Proof. We know that $M \subseteq M \cup N$ and $N \subseteq M \cup N$. We have, by Theorem 5.5(iv), $\text{GR-NeuInt}(M) \subseteq \text{GR-NeuInt}(M \cup N)$ and $\text{GR-NeuInt}(N) \subseteq \text{GR-NeuInt}(M \cup N)$. This implies $\text{GR-NeuInt}(M) \cup \text{GR-NeuInt}(N) \subseteq \text{GR-NeuInt}(M \cup N)$.

Theorem 5.5. Let M and N are subsets of P , then $\text{GR-NeuInt}(M) \cap \text{GR-NeuInt}(N) = \text{GR-NeuInt}(M \cap N)$.

Proof. We know that $M \cap N \subseteq M$ and $M \cap N \subseteq N$. We have, by Theorem 5.5(iv), $\text{GR-NeuInt}(M \cap N) \subseteq \text{GR-NeuInt}(M)$ and $\text{GR-NeuInt}(M \cap N) \subseteq \text{GR-NeuInt}(N)$.

This implies $\text{GR-NeuInt}(M \cap N) \subseteq \text{GR-NeuInt}(M) \cap \text{GR-NeuInt}(N) \dots (i)$

Again, let $x \in \text{GR-NeuInt}(M) \cap \text{GR-NeuInt}(N)$. Then $x \in \text{GR-NeuInt}(M)$ and $x \in \text{GR-NeuInt}(N)$.

Hence x is a NeutroInterior point of each of NeutroSets M and N . It follows that M and N are GR-NeuNhd of x , so that their intersection $M \cap N$ is also a GR-NeuNhd of x . Hence $x \in \text{GR-NeuInt}(M \cap N)$. Thus $x \in \text{GR-NeuInt}(M) \cap \text{GR-NeuInt}(N)$ implies that $x \in \text{GR-NeuInt}(M \cap N)$. Therefore $\text{GR-NeuInt}(M) \cap \text{GR-NeuInt}(N) \subseteq \text{GR-NeuInt}(M \cap N) \dots (ii)$

From (i) and (ii), we get $\text{GR-NeuInt}(M) \cap \text{GR-NeuInt}(N) = \text{GR-NeuInt}(M \cap N)$.

6. GRN-closure and their properties

Using the GR-NeutroClosed sets we can introduce the concept of GR-NeutroClosure operator in topological spaces.

Definition 6.1. Let M be a subset of a space P . We define the GR-NeutroClosure of M to be the intersection of all GR-NeutroClosure sets containing M . Mathematically, $\text{GR-cl}(M) = \cap \{F \mid M \subseteq F \in \text{GRC}(P)\}$.

Theorem 6.1. Let P be any topological space and $M \subseteq P$, then show that M is GR-NeutroClosure set if and only if $\text{GR-cl}(M) = M$.

Proof. Let M be a GR-NeutroClosed set in P . Then clearly the smallest GR-NeutroClosed set contained in M , is itself M . Hence $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M) = M$.

Conversely, suppose that $M \subseteq P$ and $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M) = M$. Since $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M)$ is a GR-NeutroOpen set in P , it follows that M is a GR-NeutroClosed set in P .

Theorem 6.2. Let M and N are subset of P . Then

$$\text{GR-NeuCl}(P) = P \text{ and } \text{GR-cl}(\emptyset) = \emptyset.$$

$$M \subseteq \text{GR-NeuCl}(M).$$

If N is any GR-NeuClosed set contained in M , then $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M) \subseteq N$.

If $M \subseteq N$, then $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M) \subseteq \text{GR-NeuCl}(N)$.

$$\text{GR-NeuCl}(\text{GR-NeuCl}(A)) = \text{GR-NeuCl}(A)$$

Proof. (1) Obviously.

(2) By the definition of GR-NeuClosure of M , it is obvious that $M \subseteq \text{GR-NeuCl}(M)$.

(3) Let N be any GR-NeutroClosed set containing M . Since $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M)$ is the intersection of all GR-NeutroClosed sets containing M i.e $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M)$ is contained in every GR-NeutroClosed set containing M . Hence $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M) \subseteq N$.

(4) Let M and N are Neutrosupsets of P such that $M \subseteq N$. By the definition of GR-NeutroClosure, $\text{GR-NeuCl}(N) = \cap\{F \mid N \subseteq F \in \text{GRC}(P)\}$. If $N \subseteq F \in \text{GRNC}(P)$, then $\text{GR-NeuCl}(N) \subseteq F$. Since $M \subseteq N$, $M \subseteq N \subseteq F \in \text{GRNC}(P)$, we have $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M) \subseteq F$. Therefore $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M) \subseteq \cap\{F \mid N \subseteq F \in \text{GRNC}(P)\} = \text{GR-NeuCl}(N)$. That is $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M) \subseteq \text{GR-NeuCl}(N)$.

Since $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M)$ is a GR-NeutroClosed set in P . It follows that $\text{GR-NeuCl}(\text{GR-NeuCl}(P)) = P$.

Theorem 6.3. Let M and N are subsets of P , then $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M \cup N) = \text{GR-cl}(M) \cup \text{GR-NeuCl}(N)$.

Proof. Let M and N are subsets of P . Clearly $M \subseteq M \cup N$ and $N \subseteq M \cup N$. We have by the Theorem 6.3(iv), $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M) \subseteq \text{GR-NeuCl}(M \cup N)$ and $\text{GR-NeuCl}(N) \subseteq \text{GR-NeuCl}(M \cup N)$. This implies $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M) \cup \text{GR-NeuCl}(N) \subseteq \text{GR-NeuCl}(M \cup N)$...(i).

Now to prove that $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M \cup N) \subseteq \text{GR-NeuCl}(M) \cup \text{GR-NeuCl}(N)$. Let $x \in \text{GR-NeuCl}(M \cup N)$ and $x \notin \text{GR-NeuCl}(M) \cup \text{GR-NeuCl}(N)$. Then there exists GR-NeutroClosed sets M_1 and N_1 with $M \subseteq M_1$, $N \subseteq N_1$ and $x \notin M_1 \cup N_1$. We have $M \cup N \subseteq M_1 \cup N_1$ and $M_1 \cup N_1$ is a GR-NeutroClosed set by Theorem 6.3, such that $x \notin M_1 \cup N_1$. Thus $x \notin \text{GR-NeuCl}(M \cup N)$ which is contradiction to $x \in \text{GR-NeuCl}(M \cup N)$.

Hence $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M \cup N) \subseteq \text{GR-NeuCl}(M) \cup \text{GR-NeuCl}(N)$...(ii).

From (i) and (ii), we have $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M \cup N) = \text{GR-NeuCl}(M) \cup \text{GR-NeuCl}(N)$.

Theorem 6.4. Let M and N are subsets of P , then $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M \cap N) \subseteq \text{GR-NeuCl}(M) \cap \text{GR-NeuCl}(N)$.

Proof. Let M and N are subsets of P . Clearly $M \cap N \subseteq M$ and $M \cap N \subseteq N$. We have, by Theorem 6.3(iv), $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M \cap N) \subseteq \text{GR-NeuCl}(M)$ and $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M \cap N) \subseteq \text{GR-NeuCl}(N)$. This implies $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M \cap N) \subseteq \text{GR-NeuCl}(M) \cap \text{GR-NeuCl}(N)$.

Remark 6.1. In general $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M) \cap \text{GR-NeuCl}(N) \neq \text{GR-NeuCl}(M \cap N)$, as seen from the following example.

Example 6.1. Consider $P = \{1,2,3,4\}$, topology on it $\tau = \{P, \emptyset, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{1,2\}, \{2,3\}, \{1,2,3\}\}$, $M = \{2,3\}$, and $N = \{3,4\}$, $M \cap N = \{3\}$, $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M) = \{2,3,4\}$, $\text{GR-NeuCl}(N) = \{3,4\}$, $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M \cap N) = \{3\}$ and $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M) \cap \text{GR-NeuCl}(N) = \{3,4\}$. Therefore $\text{GR-NeuCl}(M) \cap \text{GR-NeuCl}(N) \not\subseteq \text{GR-NeuCl}(M \cap N)$.

Theorem 6.5. Let M be a subset of P and $x \in P$. Then $x \in \text{GR-NeuCl}(M)$ if and only if $\forall V \cap M \neq \emptyset$ for every GR-NeuroOpen set V containing x .

Conclusion

In this study, new Generalization of Regular Neutro-open sets and Generalized regular Neutro-open set has been studied. Some properties of Regular Neutro-open sets and are studied. Also, properties of GRN-neighbourhood, GRN-interior and GRN-closure properties are investigated. Hope this work will give more benefits for further studies of Neutro-Topology.

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